

An Ontology-based Multidimensional Data Modeling

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The Problem. Aggregate data, also known as macro-data, concern with information produced in summarized form from individual level data, also known as micro-data. Typically gathered from operational databases, and possibly integrated from various data sources, aggregate information is usually managed through Business Intelligence and Data Warehousing solutions [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

Data aggregation is usually carried out by referring to the so-called *multidimensional model* [4], where events of interest for the analysis are represented as logical cubes. These cubes are characterized by *dimensions* (e.g., time or space), which correspond to the aspects of the business along which one wants to perform aggregation. Dimensions may be associated to *hierarchies* specifying different *levels* of aggregation (a.k.a. dimensional attributes [4]), and by *measures*, which are properties of the event on which to make calculations (e.g., sums or averages), and that can be used as business performance indicators (e.g., income of a shop, number of enrollments in a school). Operations performed on data cubes (also called OLAP operations) include the increment or decrement of the level of aggregation, called roll-up and drill-down, respectively, or the selection of a portion of events in the multidimensional space, called slice-and-dice.

Goal. In this project we devise a new approach for modeling and manipulating aggregate data, which is based on the use of OWL2 ontologies [7] that provide a rigorous formalization of both the application domain and the multidimensional model. The overall ontology that we devise makes it explicit the way in which macro-data are obtained from micro-data, by exploiting *views* over the domain ontology [8], which are first-class citizens in our model. Data cubes and hierarchies are indeed seen as constructed from the (SPARQL) queries associated to the views, which allow cubes dimensions, cubes measures and hierarchy levels, to be instantiated from the answers to such queries. This is a distinguishing feature of our approach, considered that other models for multidimensional data (e.g., [9, 10]) do not formalize this aspect, and methodologies for data warehouse design do not provide declarative means to specify the connection between micro- and macro-data, which is usually hidden in ETL procedures, and thus it is difficult to understand and reconstruct, e.g., for data provenance and/or lineage.

Approach. Our work is currently focused on the development of services to support both design- and run-time activities related to the production, distribution and integration of aggregate data. Such services are defined according to a formal semantics that extends the Metamodeling Semantics proposed in [11]. This semantics allows us to reason over various representation layers, i.e., the meta-level formalizing the multidimensional model, the actual data cubes designed for the analysis of the business trends, the domain ontology and the views bridging it to the cubes. A fundamental service in this scenario is query answering. Such service is indeed at the basis of several more complex functionalities, such as integration of aggregate data sets [12], possibly linked to the ontology through mappings as in OBDM [13, 14], and publishing of linked open data. Interestingly, queries in our framework may smoothly combine together elements belonging to the various mentioned levels. We finally remark that we are currently working on the implementation of software components, integrated in the OBDM tool Mastro [15, 16], that realize the multidimensional ontology-based approach devised in this project.

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